

branch without significantly increasing those on the secondary branch.

Medullary cavity was positively correlated with the number of inner and outer vascular bundles and with culm diameter. These characters may be utilized as selection criteria. Culm thickness had no relation with any of the characters, and had minimum variability.

Acc. nos. 103350, 103443, 102198, 103997, 104001, and 104003, with higher numbers of primary branches, spikelets on primary branches, and inner and outer vascular bundles and larger culm

Table 2. Relationship between 10 panicle characters in *O. glaberrima*. IRRI, 1987.

	PB	SB	SPB	SSB	TSP	IVB	OVB	CD	MC
SB	-0.46ns								
SPB	0.96**	-0.34ns							
SSB	-0.46ns	0.99**	-0.35ns						
TSP	0.56*	0.45ns	0.68**	0.44ns					
IVB	0.60*	0.03ns	0.62**	0.02ns	0.61*				
OVB	0.54*	0.04ns	0.55*	0.02ns	0.54*	0.85**			
CD	0.08ns	0.40ns	0.22ns	0.39ns	0.51*	0.49ns	0.55*		
MC	0.18ns	0.35ns	0.31ns	0.32ns	0.55*	0.67**	0.65**	0.87**	
CTh	0.05ns	0.16ns	0.11ns	0.18ns	0.25ns	-0.04ns	0.07ns	0.28ns	-0.15ns

diameter and medullary cavity may be used in breeding for increased numbers of primary branches and numbers of

spikelets on the primary branches. We have made 50 crosses involving these parents for evaluation. □

***eui* gene for elongated uppermost internode transferred to indica rice**

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The *eui*, a recessive gene controlling the elongated uppermost internode in rice, was discovered by Drs. J. N. Rutger and H. L. Carnahan at Davis, California, USA. The gene nearly doubled the length of the uppermost internode, increased panicle length 12%, and had little or no effect on other internodes or

IR50-*eui* rice plant compared to IR50. IRRI, 1987.

Comparative performance of IR50-*eui* and IR50. IRRI, 1987 DS.

Trait	IR50- <i>eui</i>	IR50	Difference ^a
Days to flowering	84	83	
Height (cm)	110.7	64.3	+46.4**
Tillers (no./hill)	25	35	-10.0**
% <i>eui</i> tillers	91.0	0	+91.0**
Yield (g/plant)	18.1	22.3	- 4.2ns

^a ** = significant at 1% level based on *t*-test of mean values. ns = nonsignificant based on *t*-test of mean values.

plant characters. It is considered equivalent to a recessive tall trait.

If the gene were incorporated into the paternal parent of hybrid rice, this parent would be taller. A taller restorer parent would aid windblown pollen dispersal on the semidwarf male sterile female parent in hybrid seed production plots. The resulting F₁ hybrid would, however, be semidwarf. Additionally, a taller restorer parent would facilitate its removal before bulk harvest of the commercial hybrid seed borne on the male sterile parent.

This gene was originally identified in a japonica line having limited use in tropical hybrid rice breeding. Original *eui* genetic stock obtained from Dr. Rutger in 1982 was crossed with semidwarf indica restorer IR50. From the F₂ population of this cross, plants showing the uppermost elongated internode were backcrossed to IR50 three times. In every BCF₂ generation, we selected plants possessing *eui* trait and resembling IR50. The BC₃F₃ progenies homozygous for *eui* gene were

selected and designated IR50-*eui* (see figure). Compared with IR50, IR50-*eui* is significantly taller, has 90% tillers with *eui* trait, but somewhat lower tillering (see table). Yields are not statistically different. Seeds of IR50-*eui* are available at IRRI.

5460ps: indica photosensitive genic male-sterile rice

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Fujian indica photosensitive genic male-sterile germplasm (FIPGMG) 5460ps, isolated from the spontaneous mutant of indica variety 5460, was released in Apr 1988 for developing two-line hybrid rice in China. 5460, as the restorer line for common three-line hybrid rice, was bred in 1983 from an early-maturing mutant (by radiation) of IR54.